

An Empirical Analysis of Pradhan Mantri Garib Kalyan Anna Yojana (PM-GKAY) With Special Reference to Sangli District

Hanamant Shahaji Sawant
Assistant Professor Department of Economics
Shrimant Babasaheb Deshmukh Mahavidyalaya, Atpadi
Affiliated to Shivaji University Kolhapur, Maharashtra

Abstract:- Food is one of the basic needs of man. Since ancient times, people have tried to satisfy their basic needs. In a welfare economy, government support and efforts to meet people's food needs are important. In a developing country with a large population like India, the government plays an important role in providing food. In India, during the terrible famine of 1940 in the province of Bengal, the first attempt was made to provide food grains to the population with the government's help. During World War II in 1945, people were provided food through rationing. After independence, the Indian government tried to reach all poor people through the public distribution system. Various programs were introduced in India to protect the poor from fluctuations in food prices, provide adequate food to every family, prevent the poor from starvation, and provide food security. Antodaya Anna Yojana and the National Food Security Act under the public distribution system have helped make the National Food Security Program a greater success.

During the Corona epidemic, the whole world came to a standstill, and during this period, the income of workers and the unorganized sector was completely stopped. Prime Minister Narendra Modi launched the Pradhan Mantri Garib Kalyan Anna Yojana on March 26, 2020, to ensure the people's food security during this crisis. The program is known as the largest food security program in the world. Thank you to this program; 66% of the people in the Sangli district received free food and were freed from hunger and emaciation. This program has successfully maintained food security during epidemics such as Corona. This program has helped improve the standard of living and social status of the poor. This program is known as a "game changer" in food security in the country.

Keywords:- Food security, Pradhan Mantri Garib Kalyan Anna Yojana.

I. INTRODUCTION

Food security is the state where all people have access to enough food to live a functional and healthy life. Food security is the assurance that all people, at all times, have access to the essential food they need from a physical and

economic perspective. In India, the then Chief Minister NT Rama Rao started the food security program with 2 rupees per kg of rice in Andhra Pradesh. To date, various food security programs have been implemented. In 1994, the food security program for the backward classes was launched; in 2001, the Annapurna program was launched; in 2003-4, the nutritious food for infants program was launched; and in 2004, the rural grain bank program was launched. Antodaya Yojana was introduced in 2000 for individuals. The program focused on nutritional malnutrition. The program provided financial assistance to address the problem of food insecurity by introducing the Gramodaya Yojana. In the area of food security, the largest program in the country is the National Food Security Act of 2013, under which the Pradhan Mantri Garib Kalyan Anna Yojana, the largest food security program in the world, was introduced in 2020.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

1) Pramod Kumar & P. Anbukani entitled "Food security in India Issues and Challenges" Food security is the milestone of national prosperity and well being. The health of nation is directly linked to food security. Besides, it is a matter of political stability and peace. India's half of the population is struggling to find food on their plate, coping with stern starvation and droughts on the flipper side. India is home to the world's largest number of hungry people, with over 200 million people. The government of India has notified the National Food Security Act (NFSA), 2013, to provide food and nutritional security in the human life cycle approach by ensuring access to adequate quality food at affordable prices for people to live a life with dignity. The Act provides for coverage of up to 75% of the rural population and up to 50% of the urban population for receiving subsidized food grains under the Targeted Public Distribution System (TPDS).

2) Shaleen Jain, "Food security in India Problems & Prospects" according to he Climate change is expected to affect agricultural land use and production due to less water availability for irrigation and other factors. There is climate change in India due to rising temperatures and extreme events in the food production systems, which impacts agricultural growth adversely. Various reports indicate that climate change would further intensify temporal and spatial variation in water availability and extreme events of flood and drought.

There is a strong need to address changes in institution and resource accessibility to tackle climate-induced natural hazards. • **Crop Diversification:** In recent years, agricultural scientists have greatly emphasized the implementation of crop diversification. The price of food grains like rice and wheat are not encouraging, and farmers have very low returns. The farmers were encouraged to earn higher profits by concentrating on other crops.

3) Neeru Chadha "Food Security in India Issues and Challenges" Achieving food security through enhancing agricultural production has been the major focus in most developing countries. Several countries have succeeded, to a noteworthy extent, in achieving this objective. However, nutritional adequacy needs to be addressed more effectively. In India, initiatives have been emphasized by introducing subsequent schemes to boost the country's food security: Public distribution system (PDS) is one of the instruments for ensuring household-level food security. The prime objective of PDS is to ensure adequate and equitable distribution of essential items of consumption to households with socially moderate prices through a regulatory mechanism. This will contribute to attaining self-sufficiency in food production and procurement and keep prices in balance. The PDS mechanism was used before independence to control food prices and shortages. However, since then, it has been deployed as a tool of inclusive economic policy – for the twin goals of equality and social justice.

➤ *Objectives of the research*

The objectives of the present research are as follows.

- To study the concept of food security.
- To review the progress of the Pradhan Mantri Garib Kalyan Anna Yojana scheme in the Sangli district.
- To study the impact of Pradhan Mantri Garib Kalyan Anna Yojana

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The present research work depends on both primary and secondary data. Considering a 95 per cent confidence level and a 5 per cent margin of error, 380 samples were drawn in ten selected talukas of PM-GKAY in the Sangli district. This sample was divided into ten talukas, and 38 ration card holders were interviewed in each taluka. For the secondary data, information was taken from articles in various journals, newspapers and annual reports of various ministries.

➤ *Significance of the Scheme*

The PM-GKAY programme provided free food grains to the poor so that the money the poor spent on food grains could be used for other needs. Under this scheme, low-income families received free food grains. It is estimated that the super poor spend 40% of their income on food, while the poor spend 30% on food. This scheme saved one-third of the income of the poor and very poor. They began to spend this saved money on material facilities, which helped them improve their status.

Under this programme, the poor received free food grains so that the money the poor spent on food grains could be used for other needs. Under this programme, low-income families received free food grains. According to one estimate, the extreme poor spend 40% of their income on food, while the poor spend 30% on food. This programme saved one-third of the income of the poor and extremely poor. They started to spend this saved money on material facilities, which helped to improve their standard of living. Food is an important factor in social security. The whole life of poor people consists of providing food. They have to spend most of their income on food. Through this scheme, food grains have been provided to the poor free of charge, reducing the monthly expenditure on food grains in the income of the poor. Due to the lack of income, the poor are unable to buy enough food grains in the market, so people from low-income families have to starve half to get food grains; they have to do inferior work in the house of big farmers, the rich, so the social standard of their life decreases. Under this scheme, poor people receive free food every month. This scheme has helped to raise the social status of people who do light work for food grains by exempting them from this work.

Table No.1 Progress of Scheme

Sr. no.	Taluka	Total Ration card Holders	Beneficiary Ration card Holder	Percentage of Beneficiary
1	Atpadi	23265	17449	75%
2	Jath	51254	36906	72%
3	Kavathe-Mahankal	23520	16464	70%
4	Kadegaon	25558	16868	66%
5	Walwa	63723	38871	61%
6	Tasgaon	41767	28401	68%
7	Khanapur	27276	18547	68%
8	Palus	28383	17597	62%
9	Shirala	26736	18447	69%
10	Miraj	101194	65776	65%
Total		412676	275323	66.75%

Source: Sangli District Food Grain Department Report 2022

In the Sangli district, 66.75% of the ration card holders have benefited from the Pradhan Mantri Garib Kalyan Anna Yojana. In percentage terms, the highest, i.e.75 % of the people in Atpadi, have benefited from this scheme, while in Walwa Taluka, the smallest, 61 % of the people have benefited. In Khanapur Atpadi Jath, Kavthe-mahankal and Tasgaon taluka in Sangli district, an average of 70 per cent of people have benefited from this scheme. Also, the correlation between ration card holders and beneficiary ration card holders is found to be 0.99, indicating that the scheme has been helpful in the implementation of food security.

IV. RESULT & DISCUSSION

The researcher wanted to study the relationship between the Pradhan Mantri Garib Kalyan Anna Yojana and its impact on the social status of the poor population. For this purpose, he used chi-square tests, which are described below. The data between A and B were collected with the questionnaire, and the following results were found.

Test No. 1 The researcher wanted to know if there was independence/dependence between
 A: Pradhan Mantri Garib Kalyan Anna Yojana &
 B: Increased social status of poor people

To examine the impact of A on B, households were given the following four options.

- Pradhan Mantri Garib Kalyan Anna Yojana increases the social status of the poor
- Although Pradhan Mantri Garib Kalyan Anna Yojana is available, the social status of the poor has not increased
- Although Pradhan Mantri Garib Kalyan Anna Yojana is not available, the social status of the poor has increased (increased awareness of rural households)
- iv)Without Pradhan Mantri Garib Kalyan Anna Yojana no social status for the poor population.

Data collected on A & B are classified in the below table.

Table no 1 Responses on A &B

	B	β	Total
A	66	13	79
α	10	11	21
Total	76	24	100

	Oi	Ei	Oi ² /Ei
	66	(A)*(B)/N=60.04	72.55
	13	(A)* (β)/N=18.96	8.91
	10	(α)* (B)/N=15.96	6.26
	11	(α)* (β)/N=5.04	24.00
Total	100	100	111.72

To test independents of A & B, chi-sq. test is applied. The test procedure is as follows;
 Ho: A & B are independent
 Vs
 H₁: A & B are dependent
 Here test statics is

$$\chi^2_{1 \text{ stat}} = \sum \frac{O_i^2}{E_i} - N \text{ where } O_i = \text{observed frequency, } E_i = \text{expected frequency \& } N = \text{total frequency}$$

Here from the above table $\chi^2_{1 \text{ stat}} = 11.72$
 $\chi^2_{1, .05 \text{ critical}} = 3.841$

As $\chi^2_{1 \text{ stat}} = 11.72 > \chi^2_{1, .05 \text{ critical}} = 3.841$, hence Ho is rejected and H₁ is accepted at 5% I.o.s.

➤ *Conclusion*

A & B are highly interdependent. The researcher concludes that Pradhan Mantri Garib Kalyan Anna Yojana has increased the social status of poor people, which means that government intervention in food security increases the social status of households.

Test no.2 The researcher wanted to know if there was independence/dependence between
 A: Pradhan Mantri Garib Kalyan Anna Yojana &
 B: Increased standard of living of the poor population

To study the impact of A on B, the following four options were presented to the households.

- Pradhan Mantri Garib Kalyan Anna Yojana increases the standard of living of the poor population.
- Although Pradhan Mantri Garib Kalyan Anna Yojana is available, the standard of living of the poor population did not increase.
- Although Pradhan Mantri Garib Kalyan Anna Yojana is not available, the standard of living of the poor population has increased (increased income/awareness of rural households)
- Without Pradhan Mantri Garib Kalyan Anna Yojana, no increased standard of living. Data collected on A & B is classified in the below table.

Table no.2 Responses on A &B

	B	β	Total
A	62	18	80
α	08	12	20
Total	70	30	100

	Oi	Ei	Oi ² /Ei
	62	(A)*(B)/N=56	68.64
	18	(A)* (β)/N=24	13.5
	08	(α)* (B)/N=14	4.57
	12	(α)* (β)/N=06	24.00
Total	100	100	110.71

To test independents of A & B, chi-sq. test is applied. The test procedure is as follows

Ho: A & B are independent
 Vs
 H₁: A & B are dependent

Here test statics is
 $\chi^2_{1 \text{ stat}} = \sum \frac{O_i^2}{E_i} - N \text{ where } O_i = \text{observed frequency, } E_i = \text{expected frequency \& } N = \text{total frequency}$
 Here from the above table $\chi^2_{1 \text{ stat}} = 10.71$

$\chi^2_{1, .05}$ critical = 3.841

As χ^2_{1} stat= 10.71 $>$ $\chi^2_{1, .05}$ critical = 3.841, hence H_0 is rejected and H_1 is accepted at 5% l.o.s.

➤ *Conclusion*

A & B are highly interdependent; the researcher concludes that Pradhan Mantri Garib Kalyan Anna Yojana has raised the standard of living of poor people.

V. CONCLUSION

In a country with such a large population, this program providing abundant food grains from the government has greatly improved food security for the poor. Pradhan Mantri Garib Kalyan Anna Yojana is the world's largest food security program that provides free wheat, rice and pulses to the population. The Pradhan Mantri Garib Kalyan Anna Yojana is the world's largest food security program providing beneficiaries with free wheat, rice and pulses. This program was introduced during the Corona epidemic. During the Corona epidemic, there were three periods of unemployment in the country. During these layoffs, the income of the poor was completely stopped. Thank you for the availability of food for the poor through this program; their problem of hunger and starvation was solved. If this program had not been launched during the epidemic, the poor would not have been able to buy food grains in the market due to lack of purchasing power, i.e. money. Therefore, starvation due to lack of food was prevented during the epidemics.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Chadha, N. (Jan 2016). Food Security in India Issue & Challenges . *BEST International Journal of Humanities Arts, Medicine & Sciences* .
- [2]. Dr. Bimal Patel, D. N. (2014). *Food Security Law-Interdisciplinary Perspectives*. Eastern Book Company.
- [3]. Jain, S. (n.d.). Food Security in India: Problems & Prospects. *Internatinal Journal of Sustainable Development* .
- [4]. Pramod kumar, P. A. (n.d.). Food Security in India Issues & Challenges. *Internatinal Journal of Applied & Pure Science & Agriculture* .
- [5]. Sawant, H. (2020). Role of Bharat Nirman Yojana and Rural Infrastructure in India . *Studies in Indian Place Names* , 355 to 361.
- [6]. *Annual Report (2022). Ministry of Consumer Affairs, Food & Public Distribution* . New Delhi : Government of India.
- [7]. <https://www.drishtias.com>. (n.d.).